

Transverse Creep Response of SiC (Trimarc1®)/Ti-22Al-23Nb MMC's

D .B. Miracle¹, J.E. Spowart¹, and B.S. Majumdar²

¹Materials and Manufacturing Directorate, AF Research Laboratory
, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH, USA 45433

²UES, Inc., 4401 Dayton-Xenia Rd, Dayton, OH USA 45432

KEYWORDS: Transverse creep, orthorhombic titanium alloy, embedded fibers

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Continuously-reinforced orthorhombic Ti-alloy composites (OTMC's) are under development for compressor ring rotor applications in advanced gas turbine engines. Stresses in these components are principally along the hoop (i.e., fiber) direction, and the axial properties of OTMC's are generally sufficient to support these stresses. The greatest opportunity for improving material performance is under transverse creep conditions, especially for full-life applications. It is therefore important to understand the transverse creep response of OTMC's. Most of the previous transverse creep data have been collected on samples where the fibers intersect a free edge, but recent work on SiC (SCS-6)/Ti-6Al-4V composites has shown that the transverse creep of samples with embedded fibers was significantly improved at low and intermediate stresses over identically-prepared samples with exposed fiber ends (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Transverse creep data for SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V specimens at 482°C. Data for exposed, embedded, and the "neat" matrix are included. Also, the Crossman model predictions are plotted.

In this paper, the transverse creep response of a 4-ply SiC (Trimarc1)/Ti-22Al-23Nb (at %) composite will be presented. Tests will performed at 650°C from 69 - 276 MPa. Creep

samples with fibers exposed at the edges as well as specimens with fully embedded fibers will be tested. The response of each sample geometry will be compared to creep data from the unreinforced matrix ("neat" material). Post-test metallography will be used to determine the mode and progression of damage. The creep data will be analyzed with a modified Crossman model, which takes account of the debond stress and the fiber/matrix interface in these composites.